

USING WINDOWS SERVER 2012-BASED STORAGE SOLUTIONS FOR SMALL AND MEDIUM SIZE BUSINESS RESOURCES

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Abstract. Introduction of Windows Server 2012 took many IT companies by surprise. From virtualization and cloud part of the market all the way to the storage market, with new Server 2012-integrated technologies, there's a lot to choose from. We'll try to cover these new technologies in this article.

Introduction

One of the most important part of IT system today is storage, where people store all of their data and where more and more data gets stored in terms of virtual machines. Different approaches exist, as well as different technologies that companies can use. If companies can handle the investment and want enterprise-level features, they tend to look for Fiber Channel-based solutions as FC is considered to be robust solution and the best one. If we take a look at the midrange solutions, there's an awful lot of iSCSI-based solutions on the market, mostly based on Linux or BSD operating systems. Microsoft's Server platforms haven't been used much for this kind of usage model.

A couple of years ago, storage companies started introducing Windows-based storage solutions. Companies like Thecus and QNAP brought solution-blind products based on Windows Storage Server to the market, but these products didn't capture the market. Big companies like Bosch and other companies with physical security divisions started exploiting the possibility of bundling Windows Server-based storage solutions with their other security-related products, like video surveillance etc. These systems were pre-configured to be installed for a specific purpose only, rather than being ready to accept other duties in any company's IT backbone.

Windows Server 2012 has a chance to change all that. With some new technologies developed by Microsoft, now Windows Server 2012-based storage solutions have a chance to capture a bigger part of the market.

Storage Spaces

Storage Spaces is one of the new technologies in Windows Server 2012. The basic idea behind Storage Spaces is that we need to be able to manipulate storage space in a more sustainable way then before when using Microsoft Server platform. Microsoft did have a technology that was a bit similar in the past (Dynamic Disks), but it was mostly side-stepped as unreliable and it was difficult to repair once something broke down. Storage Spaces feature goes a long way to maintain resiliency of data, while at the same time using hard disk space on multiple volumes in a variety of ways. This alone will enable us to be much more independent in terms of how we think about directories, expanding and shrinking disk sizes etc.

Storage Spaces also offer a nice way of getting rid of some RAID teething problems. With RAID subsystems, when a power outage happens, it can lead to a variety of situations that will result in a loss of data. If a controller failure happens after a couple of years of non-stop operation, then there's a chance we'll have to buy one second-hand, if we're lucky to find it - only to try to salvage our data. With Storage Spaces, if a controller fails, you can still take your hard drives and install them in a separate server and get all of the data from them, in a similar way in which you could do the same thing in a same situation if you were using Linux as your operating system and LVM as your storage technology of choice.

When adding hard drives to a Storage Spaces pool, there are some things that we need to watch out for. For example, you cannot boot from a Storage Space volume. When you add a hard drive to the Storage Spaces pool, all data will be lost so you should either add a completely new hard drive (without partitions) or suffer the consequences. To add a hard drive to the pool, it has to be without any partitions. Also, you can not add Fiber Channel and/or iSCSI volumes to Storage Spaces pool.

If we take a look at Storage Spaces's three-layered architecture, we will discover that Storage Spaces and Linux LVM (Logical Volume Manager) are very much alike. Both aim to use multiple partitions to create larger "little storage clouds" which can then be sliced into multiple volumes, formatted and used in a variety of ways. But there are also some fundamental differences between these two technologies. Let's cover these similarities and differences in the following table:

Table 1. Feature comparison, Logical Volume Manager and Windows Server 2012 Storage Spaces

Feature	Logical Volume Manager	Windows Server 2012 Storage Spaces
Span across multiple volumes	Yes	Yes
Ability to use software RAID	Yes	No
Ability to use hardware RAID	Yes	Yes
Snapshotting	Yes	Yes
Ability to be used as RAW device	Yes	Yes
Ability to be used as iSCSI RAW device	Yes	No
Thin Provisioning	With RHEL7, end of Y2013	Yes
Data parity distribution	No (only combined with RAID)	Yes, evenly

SMB3.0 (Server Message Block 3.0)

One of the most interesting new technologies that are really going help smaller and medium-sized companies to scale-in and scale-out on a storage level is the new SMB 3.0 in combination with Hyper-V 3.0-based virtual machines and cloud technologies. If we take into account the fact that we can now have failover clusters of virtual machines based on Hyper-V 3.0, all stored on a File Server using Windows Server 2012 and SMB 3.0 as a built-in protocol, this changes the picture a lot. Previously, if you wanted to do that, you had to buy separate storage hardware to do that (or build your own). You can also easily create a failover cluster of file servers, and share that failover storage by using SMB 3.0 file-sharing protocol. Then, on top of that, you can implement Hyper-V failover cluster, and have a complete failover solution for your company. This feature alone can be a reason for a huge market-wide shift towards using Microsoft Server 2012 as a basis for virtualization and cloud-type environments, which is slowly happening on the market. If used like that, SMB 3.0 failover clusters can be a much cheaper solution to classic storage, while maintaining the familiar user interface for maintenance.

There are other very important features in SMB 3.0, as well. One of the biggest problems with older SMB protocols (2.0, 2.1) was low performance when working with small files and folders, both in read and write operations. This, in turn, was a big problem for many services that can use SMB-based storage, like Microsoft SQL Server OLTP (Online Transaction Processing). Changes that were implemented on the network stack of SMB 3.0 protocol now include much better performance for larger files, by using bigger MTUs (Maximum Transmission Unit) which is very helpful when we're working with i.e. large files, like VHDs (Virtual Hard Disk).

Also, if you want to share a folder by using SMB 3.0, you can now select a "profile" which will be best suited to the share's actual usage. For example, there are different profiles for using a SMB 3.0 storage with databases, Hyper-V virtualization, and other applications.

Other SMB 3.0 features include SMB encryption, SMB Direct, SMB Multichannel, SMB Signing and SMB Transparent Failover. Let's briefly describe all of them.

SMB encryption

With SMB encryption, you can securely transfer your files over any kind of network, without the need to implement end-to-end IPsec or any other encrypted protocol. This is a very good hardening measure as it increases the overall security level for sharing of files and folders.

SMB Direct

SMB Direct is a framework that can make use of RDMA-enabled network adapters (Remote Direct Memory Access). If we have such an adapter we can have offloaded, faster data transfers with very low latency without CPU hogging. By using SMB Direct, we're actually doing memory-to-memory transfers, without CPU utilization. RDMA-based protocols include iWARP (RDMA with TCP/IP), ROCE (RDMA over Converged Ethernet) and Infiniband

SMB Multichannel

By using network teaming, we can significantly increase throughput of SMB file server in our infrastructure. We can also use combination of NIC teaming and fault tolerance to get the best of both worlds - security and speed.

SMB signing

SMB signing uses AES protocols for signing. Older versions of SMB (2.0, 2.1) used SHA-type of algorithm, which is much slower than the new AES-enabled protocol.

SMB Transparent Failover

If we create a SMB 3.0 file server with failover, we can easily take nodes offline and do maintenance on them while the service they offer isn't stopped - it's running as if we weren't doing maintenance. In case there's a failover, clients receive a message and transparently contact another cluster node (another server). This functionality mimics multicontroller-type of storage without specifically paying for it.

SMB 3.0 also includes a lot of new PowerShell cmdlets and WMI objects, which will make configuration and maintenance much easier in larger environments with bigger scale-out file server clusters. These are available in Windows Server 2012 only, and require PowerShell 3.0.

ReFS

ReFS (Resilient File System) is an all-new Microsoft filesystem. It is based on older NTFS and directly integrated with Storage Spaces, and as we'll discuss later, this integration offers a vast array of additional functionalities. Basic advancements in ReFS offer better data integrity, better availability, better scalability better error detection. As one of the most important features, it solves one of the biggest NTFS problems - it doesn't maintain metadata in place - rather, it uses allocate-on-write, and writes metadata to a separate location which means better recovery options. It offers larger maximum volume and file sizes, which is always important for databases and other usage models ($2^{64}-1$ bytes for maximum file size, 2^{64} files in any given directory, 2^{64} folders on a volume, and up to 2^{78} bytes of volume size when using 16KB cluster size). Also, it ensures data integrity by using metadata with checksumming, disk scrubbing for protection against disk errors, and striping for performance.

If we use ReFS with Storage Spaces, there's a lot of additional features which we can use. We could develop a scale-out solution with Storage Spaces as the low-level technology, and then built ReFS partitions on top of Storage Spaces. Then we can use all of the benefits of Storage Spaces (easy to use, easy to reallocate space, thin provisioning etc.) with a very robust and secure filesystem that's highly compatible with NTFS. The only feature that's missing right now is that you can't add Storage Spaces volume formatted with ReFS to a CSV (Cluster Shared Volume). This has been changed for Windows Server 2012 R2 Preview, and is expected to be a supported feature in the next release announced for later this year.

Deduplication

Windows Server 2012 offers data deduplication capabilities, which will surely be a welcome feature for any type of business using Microsoft Server platforms. First thing that you can notice about the deduplication capability in Windows Server 2012 is that it scales very nicely with the number of cores and memory provided. After a two-month testing period, we'll try to illustrate this in a following table:

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Table 2. Scalability of Windows Server 2012 deduplication

	2-core, 4GB, 2x256GB SSD	4-core, 4GB, 2x256GB SSD	4-core, 8GB, 2x256GB SSD	6-core, 12GB, 2x256GB SSD
Relative performance	100%	119,5%	125,9%	157,4%

There is no real value in saying that deduplication in Windows Server 2012 offers a fix amount of deduplication as it will depend from situation to situation. In general, there are a couple of scenarios. If you were to deduplicate a file share with a lot of documents, deduplication in Windows Server 2012 will be worth your time and effort. We've had a case in our test lab where we copied roughly 300,000 files in approximately 30,000 directories from a local company, with deduplication varying from 50-70%, depending on the number of items we added. Of course, deduplication will be much less useful on bigger VHD files. Our tests indicate that - on average - we got up to 10% deduplication levels, which is low but expected. This is one of the features in Windows Server 2012 that storage administrators will like as it's easy to do maintenance with, while managers and company owners will like it as it will mean less investment in hard drive space and storage. Which can in turn mean that we could invest these savings elsewhere - to buy new servers, new network devices, or just save it for future purposes.